

**THE INFLUENCE OF SOY FERTILIZER STANDARDS ON
PRODUCTIVITY IN MEDIUM SALINITY SOILS**

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Abstract. In this article, the effect of optimized fertilizer rates on productivity during the cultivation of different soybean varieties as a repeated crop under the conditions of medium salinity soils is highlighted. Today, improving the fertilizer application system during the cultivation of promising soybean varieties is one of the main tasks of agriculture. In the experiment, we applied phosphorus fertilizer in four different rates: 50 kg in the first option, 75 kg in the second option. and in the third option 100 kg and in the fourth option 150 kg (clean) standards are used. Also, indicators such as germination, growth and productivity of soybeans, depending on the amount of fertilizer application, were also studied.

Keywords. Protein, soy, oil, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, grain, legume, yield, fertility, soil, saline soil, biochemical processes.

**O‘RTACHA SHO‘RLANGAN TUPROQLARDA SOYA O‘G‘ITLASH
MEYORLARINI HOSILDORLIKKA TA’SIRI**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘rtacha sho‘rlangan tuproqlar sharoitida turli soya navlarini takroriy ekin sifatida yetishtirish davomida optimallashtirilgan o‘g‘it meyorlarini hosildorlikka ta’siri yoritilgan. Bugungi kunda istiqbolli soya navlarini yetishtirish davomida o‘g‘it qo‘llash tizimini takomillashtirish qishloq xo‘jaligining asosiy vazifalaridan biridir. Biz tajribada fosforli o‘g‘itni to‘rt xil me‘yorda soldik: birinchi variantda 50 kg., ikkinchi variantda 75 kg. va uchinchi variantda 100 kg va to‘rtinchi variantda 150 kg (sof holda) me‘yorlar qo‘llaniladi. Shuningdek, o‘g‘itlar qo‘llash miqdorlariga bog‘liq holda soyaning unuvchanligi, o‘sib rivojlanishi, hosildorligi kabi ko‘rsatkichlari ham o‘rganilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar. Oqsil, soya, yog‘, azot, fosfor, kaliy, don, dukkak, hosil, unuvchanlik, tuproq, sho‘rlangan tuproq, biokimyoviy jarayonlar.

**ВЛИЯНИЕ НОРМ СОЕВЫХ УДОБРЕНИЙ НА ПРОДУКТИВНОСТЬ
СРЕДНЕЗАОЛЕННЫХ ПОЧВ**

Абстрактный. В данной статье освещено влияние оптимизированных норм удобрений на продуктивность при возделывании различных сортов сои в качестве повторной культуры в условиях среднесоленных почв. Сегодня совершенствование системы внесения удобрений при выращивании перспективных сортов сои является одной из основных задач сельского хозяйства. В опыте мы вносили фосфорные удобрения в четырех разных нормах: 50 кг в первом варианте, 75 кг во втором варианте. а в третьем варианте используются стандарты 100 кг и в четвертом варианте 150 кг

(чистые). Также были изучены такие показатели, как всхожесть, рост и урожайность сои в зависимости от количества внесения удобрений.

Ключевые слова. Белок, соя, масло, азот, фосфор, калий, зерно, бобовые, урожайность, плодородие, почва, засоленная почва, биохимические процессы.

Only 20.7% of agricultural land in our country is irrigated land. Today, Uzbekistan has a total of 4.3 million hectares of irrigated land, and as of October 1, 2020, 44.7 percent of these irrigated lands are of varying degrees, including 31.0 percent weak, 11.9 percent moderate, and 1.9 percent strong. highly saline [1].

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 53 of January 30, 2020, indicated the indicators of placement of repeated (common) agricultural crops on farms and homestead land plots in 2020, in which the area of repeated crops in Fergana region is 28,680.3 hectares, of which 96 hectares of land are sowing of soybeans is envisaged.

According to the indicators of the placement of agricultural crops on the main areas for the 2020 harvest, given in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1025 of December 20, 2019, it is planned to plant winter wheat on 1 million 63 thousand hectares of irrigated land in our Republic, and after the release of these areas, 73 percent of them will be replanted.

Among leguminous crops, soybean is considered the best quality food crop with its unique chemical composition, and it is known that the amount of some essential amino acids in the grain is higher than that of peas and mung beans. This vegetable grain, which has the property of enriching the soil with nitrogen, contains the amino acids isoleucine, leucine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, threonine and valine, which are the most important for humans. Today, there are 130 million shadow areas in the world. more than a hectare, this plant takes the first place among legumes in terms of cultivated area. Since its grain contains up to 50% protein and 25-28% oil, it belongs to the group of the most valuable crops. Today, more than 400 different products necessary for the national economy are made from soybeans. Soy is an environmentally friendly quality raw material used in the food industry [2].

35% of the vegetable oil consumed by the population in Jakhan, which contains almost no harmful substances, is obtained from soybeans. After extracting the oil from the seed, soy isolate is produced and its protein content reaches 75%. Baby food, cookies, useful additives for bread, proteins for the sausage industry, products for the confectionery industry (caffeine-free chocolates) are made from it. In industry, it is used in the production of linoleum, in obtaining the highest quality and most expensive car paints. Soy protein is used in the production of egg powder containing lecithin, blood plasma, high-quality lenses for glasses. [3].

One kilogram of soybeans can produce 4 liters of milk for humans and 8 liters for calves, as well as all animal products - milk, yogurt, cottage cheese, cheese, meat (sheep, beef, chicken, goose).

In view of the above, the authors provide recommendations for increasing soybean as a repeat crop and soybean production under moderate salinity soils.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to grow soybeans and fully meet the population's needs for soybean oil" in 2017-2021, the area under soybean cultivation will be gradually increased, during this period the main area will be 92.2 thousand hectares, 40 It is planned to plant 6,000 hectares as a repeated crop.

In the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, this plant can be harvested twice a year. Since soybean is a leguminous crop, it has the ability to absorb free nitrogen from the atmosphere, activate phosphorus in the soil, and increase soil fertility.

381 kcal of energy is released from 100 g of soybeans.

Soybeans are the main source of protein, and they contain: potassium, zinc, magnesium, phosphorus, calcium, iron, vitamins E and B6, folic acid and beta carotene.

Soybean cultivation and development phases in moderately saline soils of Fergana region, changes in botanical signs, and study of whether the chemical composition of grain can change depending on agrotechnical measures are considered urgent tasks. The aim of the study was to grow soybean varieties "Orzu", "Nafis" and "Nena" in moderately saline soils of Fergana region and to study their development phases, to observe the process of formation of nodules in the soil and to determine the yield structure of the varieties. During the experiment, the seeds of the above-mentioned soybean varieties were sown in three different sowing rates, and three different sowing systems were used, and plant growth, development, and productivity were studied. The development phases of "Orzu", "Nafis" and "Nena" cultivars in medium salinity soils of Fergana region and the dynamics of biometric development of vegetative organs, the formation of productivity elements under the influence of changes in planting rate and planting system were determined. On July 20, 2020, three varieties - "Orzu", "Nafis" and "Nena" - were planted in moderately saline soils of Fergana region. First, the crop area for experimental options was determined, leveled well, prepared for planting, and strings were drawn. Variants were drawn in the field notebook and the location was determined. Before planting soybean seeds, the soil was sprayed with phosphorus fertilizer according to the standards. The reason why we use phosphorus mineral fertilizers when planting soybeans is that phosphorus fertilizers increase the plant's cold resistance. Due to frequent unexpected frosts in Khorezm region in March, it was decided to experiment with the feeding of young soybean lawns with phosphorus fertilizers in order to increase their resistance to frosts. In the experiment, we applied phosphorus fertilizer in four different rates: 50 kg in the first option, 75 kg in the second option. and 100 kg in the third option and 150 kg (purely) in the fourth option. Soybeans in all forms germinated on March 18-

20. No difference was noticed in the germination phase of soybean varieties. There was no significant difference in the next development phase - the branching period, the branching period was observed on April 2-5. Flowering period was observed in "Orzu" variety on April 2-4, phosphorus fertilizers were not noticed in the initial development phase of the soybean plant, only when it came to the flowering phase, when the rate of 100 kg of phosphorus was increased, this period was accelerated by 1-2 days. In "Nena" variety, the difference was not noticeable in the tillering phase, in the later phases, the development period started one to two days earlier in the control option than in the options with phosphorus fertilizers. The flowering period in the "Orzu" variety was observed on April 12-13, and the difference between the variants was 1-3 days. In the "Nena" variety, this period was observed on April 14-16. Due to the increase in fertilizer rates in this variety, the period was delayed by 1-3 days. The pod formation period was observed in the second half of April. After budding, the flowering phase began after 5-7 days in the "Dream" variety, and 8-9 days after the "Nena" variety. Due to the given rate of mineral fertilizer, the flowering phase started 2-3 days later in "Dream" variety and 3-4 days later in "Nena" variety. Increasing the rate of phosphorus fertilizers given in both varieties affected the further development phases. It has been found that the ripening phase of pods is the longest phase of development. The ripening phase is the shortest development phase in soybean varieties. It became known that the ripening phase begins at the end of May and the first decade of June. The ripening period was observed for "Orzu" variety on May 26-27, and for "Nena" variety on June 2-4. Experimental data revealed that the development phases of soybean varieties were accelerated in the control variants without mineral fertilizers. It was found that soybeans fed in moderation with mineral fertilizers had a reduction in the development phase of both varieties. According to the experiment, the ripening of "Orzu" and "Nena" soybean varieties accelerated by 2-3 days in the control variant. Therefore, if there is not enough nutrients in the soil, the stems of the plant are lower and the development is slower, the number of leaves, the number of pods and the number of grains in the pod are less. When phosphorus fertilizer was applied, the development phases of soybean varieties "Orzu" and "Nena" were delayed by 2-4 days.

The productivity of soybean varieties varied depending on the application rate of phosphorus fertilizers, the highest grain yield was obtained from variants with 100 kg of phosphorus per hectare and 18 t/ha of "Dream" variety, 21 t/ha of "Nena" variety. The lowest soybean grain yield was ripened in control options, "Orzu" variety yielded 13.7 t/ha, and "Nena" variety yielded 14.6 centners of grain per hectare in options without phosphorus fertilizer. The amount of phosphorus is 150 kg. , did not make a significant difference in the grain yield per hectare, nor did it cover the costs incurred as the yield was 1.1 quintals. Therefore, we considered the

best option in our experience to be options with 100 kg of phosphorus fertilizer. Conclusion: planting of soybean varieties on moderately saline soils of Khorezm region showed that soybean varieties named "Orzu" and "Nena" were planted in the decade of March in Khorezm region with a sharp continental climate, and the crop ripened at the end of May. 100 kg for the soya planted areas. application of phosphorus fertilizers resulted in higher yield and soybean cultivars with phosphorus fertilization had a 4-5 day longer growing season than the non-fertilized control. Therefore, it is possible to plant soybean varieties in moderately saline soils of the Khorezm region and grow ecological food products for the population.

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